

BIODYNAMO NOTEBOOK SERVICE

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

The BioDynaMo project is a general platform for agent-based computer simulations of biological tissue dynamics. It allows us to simulate multi-scale biological systems in a 3D physical system, accounting for mechanical interactions, diffusion of substances, and biological behaviors. The system is in active development. I've worked on developing the BioDynaMo Tutorials Dashboard and cloud service for BioDynaMo Notebooks (which are built with Jupyter Notebooks together with a ROOT C++ Kernel) and improving the whole UI aspect of using the BioDynaMo Notebooks.

ABSTRACT

Because of the improvements in the fields of experimentation techniques, computer hardware, and software, the field of computer modeling and simulation of biological systems is rapidly advancing. But the main problem at hand is the absence of a standardized and high-performance platform for conducting in-silico biomedical experiments and that's where BioDynaMo comes to play. *BioDynaMo is an open-source C++ framework where life scientists can easily create, run, and visualize 3D agent-based biological simulations (BioDynaMo, n.d).*

It supports the use of Jupyter Notebooks to create, run, and visualize simulations in and these notebooks are supported by the ROOT framework. Since simulations in BioDynaMo are written in C++, so-called ROOT Notebooks are used to get the same functionalities one would expect in regular (Python-based) Jupyter Notebooks. Prior to the use of these notebooks, it was required to have BioDynaMo installed and additionally execute some commands to have them stored locally on their machine. That would take up a lot of additional time and moreover, it could've led to many complications because of the framework's requirements. That's even worse for someone who just wants to see how one of these simulations looks and does not deal with any code-modifying process. The first step for improving this system was making Jupyter notebooks generated to HTML format which could easily be accessed from BioDynaMo's website in less than a second. The next step was the improvement of notebook usage with the cloud service so that everyone can easily and quickly try out some simulations by themselves and see whether they want to proceed with the whole installation process. The cloud service for this framework was done with Binder which converts GitHub repositories to the collection of interactive notebooks. Binder was used before for these interactive notebooks, but on its own for this kind of framework it took too long to build the Docker image, that's where our custom Docker images helped out and made sure that users can have access to this SaaS as fast as possible.

The improvement of using this system is more than just noticeable: these notebooks fetched from BioDynaMo software are now easily accessible from the biodynamo.org website. Also, having to have installed BioDynaMo with all of its requirements (such as Python with additional modules, etc..) could take up over half an hour. Getting these notebooks generated as a cloud service just from using Binder's environment could take up over 10 minutes, and using Docker's environment reduced that time to less than 2 minutes.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Because of the improvements in the fields of experimentation techniques, computer hardware, and software, the field of computer modeling and simulation of biological systems is rapidly advancing. *Many multicellular systems problems can only be understood by studying how cells move, grow, divide, interact, and die. Tissue-scale dynamics emerge from systems of many interacting cells as they respond to and influence their microenvironment* (APL Bioengineering 2, 2018).

a. Biological modeling

Computer models aim to incorporate multi-scale biological data into comprehensive, dynamic computer software that simulates a biological system. Such models may help in understanding and even predicting the outcome of the modeled biological processes. Advancement in computer modeling is fueled by both advance in biological experimentation techniques which significantly increase the amount of data acquired in a given experiment—and advance in computer hardware technology—which boosts the resources available to the modeler. Biological models are at the core of Systems Biology, a novel approach to analyzing biological systems as a dynamic whole, which may overcome some of the limitations posed by more reductionist approaches.

1.a.1 Approaches to Biological Modeling

There are two sorts of biological modeling: mathematical and computational. Whilst mathematical models usually use some mathematical tools – mostly differential equations to calculate dynamic relationships between bulk quantities, computational models use computer algorithms to describe systems.

b. Simulations

The main problem at hand is the absence of a standardized and high-performance platform for conducting in-silico biomedical experiments (i.e. simulations). A simulation is an indispensable tool in aiding biomedical researchers to understand complex biological systems and, ultimately, to develop a new medicine. The result of a simulation can be delivered in different ways, from visualization, through graphs of the simulated run, to numerical results. Life scientists traditionally follow the 'single researcher's project' approach, in which a model is developed to investigate a specific scientific question and is abandoned after the question has been answered and the work has been published. This inhibits other scientists to build upon prior work and effectively slows down the pace of biomedical research, making it a societal problem at large.

c. Available frameworks

There are already some general-purpose simulation systems built. These simulation systems can be classified, apart from their aforementioned modeling paradigm, by their modeled biological scale: from the intracellular level to the complete organism level. Intracellular scale simulations model different phenomena occurring inside a cell or on its surface, concentrating on a single cell per simulation run. Standout examples of intracellular, general-purpose systems are Virtual Cell, BIOCHAM, BioNetGen; Cellular Dynamic Simulator (CDS), Smoldyn, and COPASI which simulate different intracellular processes using different modeling paradigms. Some systems listed above may be used either standalone or

incorporated into other systems (e.g., Virtual Cell incorporates Smoldyn and COPASI) to serve as an algorithmic solution for a certain component in the process.

d. BioDynaMo

BioDynaMo is a knowledge transfer project at CERN Openlab, with the goal to ‘recycle knowledge’ that is present at CERN to the fields of life science. At the core, it is an open-source C++ framework where life scientists can easily create, run, and visualize 3D agent-based biological simulations. The idea is that the users of BioDynaMo implement their biological models with minimal coding effort and rely on our highly optimized execution engine that deals with the intricacies that are involved in the world of high-performance computing. The software architecture has therefore been designed to be modular and extensible – this facilitates reuse of prior work among life scientists. The focus wasn’t just on tackling the computational challenges, but also, it’s the human aspect that’s been taken into account when designing BioDynaMo’s user interface. This is where BioDynaMo Notebooks come into play.

1.d.1 BioDynaMo Notebooks

BioDynaMo supports the use of Jupyter Notebooks to create, run, and visualize simulations in and these notebooks are supported by the ROOT framework. This is a more user-friendly interface to BioDynaMo’s C++ API, and it has been serving three purposes so far:

- Education
- Prototyping (i.e. in the form of tutorials and simple demos). See Figure 1.
- A web-based dashboard for configuring and executing multiple simulations running in parallel with different runtime parameters and collecting and analyzing the data that are produced

Figure 1. BioDynaMo Notebook running a neuroscience demo locally

Notebooks can be used to play around interactively with code snippets (e.g. to test code, or to easily change parameters). Another great use is to create tutorials that can be presented to others for demonstrative or educational purposes. The visualization to bring across certain points about your simulation in an effective manner can be embedded. Since simulations in BioDynaMo are written in C++, so-called ROOT Notebooks are used to get the same functionalities one would expect in regular (Python-based) Jupyter Notebooks.

Prior to the use of these notebooks, it was required to have BioDynaMo installed and additionally execute some commands to have them stored locally on their machine. That would take up a lot of additional time and moreover, it could've led to many complications because of the framework's requirements. It's even worse for someone who just wants to see how one of these simulations looks and not deal with any code-modifying process. The first step for improving this system was making Jupyter notebooks generated to HTML format which could easily be accessed from BioDynaMo's website in less than a second. The next step was the improvement of notebook usage with the cloud service so that everyone can easily try out some simulations by themselves and see whether they want to proceed with the whole installation process easily and quickly.

2. SYSTEM OVERVIEW

BioDynaMo is an open-source C++ framework where life scientists can easily create, run, and visualize 3D agent-based biological simulations. The idea is that the users of BioDynaMo implement their biological models with minimal coding effort and rely on our highly optimized execution engine that deals with the intricacies that are involved in the world of high-performance computing. The software architecture has therefore been designed to be modular and extensible – this facilitates reuse of prior work among life scientists. The focus wasn't just on tackling the computational challenges, but also, it's the human aspect that's been taken into account when designing BioDynaMo's user interface. That's because this framework is based on the so-called Notebooks.

a. BioDynaMo Notebooks

Notebooks are supported by the ROOT framework. Since simulations in BioDynaMo are currently written in C++, 'ROOT Notebooks' are used to get the same functionalities one would expect in regular (Python-based) Jupyter Notebooks. Under the hood, it makes use of the C++ interpreter 'rootcling', which makes executing code snippets on-the-fly possible. They can be run locally by installing BioDynaMo and executing command 'root --notebook'. But also, there is another way of using them now: with BioDynaMo's cloud interface, there is no need for installing anything on the machine so it's even more accessible to everyone. It's expected to reach more users in the future thanks to its uniqueness and simplicity.

There are three main functional purposes of BioDynaMo Notebooks:

- to teach people new to biodynamo about the platform in an educational way
- to demonstrate simulations to anyone with a link to the Binder page
- to create and develop new simulation prototypes rapidly

b. New Features

The important improvement on BioDynaMo Notebooks was the development of accessible, easy-to-use, simple, quick, and scalable cloud service for them and making them available in HTML format if someone is just planning to see and not use the notebooks.

3. IMPLEMENTATION

The BioDynaMo Notebooks service was developed using Jupyter Notebooks, JupyterLab & ROOT framework (together with creating a so-called ROOT notebook), GatsbyJS (which is ReactJS-based and GraphQL is used for querying site data), together with the tools Binder & Docker and some shell scripts. In this chapter, all of these technologies will be explained, but the focus will be mostly on the BioDynaMo Notebook cloud service since the Notebook service with regular, local-running notebooks has already been developed before.

a. Technologies

3.a.1 Jupyter Notebook

Jupyter Notebook is a web application that allows you to interactively work with code snippets. It allows you to write text (in Markdown and/or HTML format) to give information about the contents of code snippets or to give context. Besides code snippets, you can embed visualizations (e.g. BioDynaMo visualizations), and other forms of media (e.g. images, videos, etc.). A Notebook is composed of "cells" with certain contents. There are different types of cells to contain the different types of content (e.g. code snippets, text, media) and can be executed on-the-fly within a web browser.

Figure 2. Example of a Jupyter Notebook (www.ipython.org)

3.a.2 JupyterLab

JupyterLab enables you to work with documents and activities such as Jupyter notebooks, text editors, terminals, and custom components in a flexible, integrated, and extensible manner (JupyterLab, n.d).

You can arrange multiple documents and activities side by side in the work area using tabs and splitters. Documents and activities integrate with each other, enabling new workflows for interactive computing, for example:

1. Code Consoles provide transient scratchpads for running code interactively, with full support for rich output. A code console can be linked to a notebook kernel as a computation log from the notebook, for example.
2. Kernel-backed documents enable code in any text file (Markdown, Python, R, LaTeX, etc...) to be run interactively in any Jupyter kernel.
3. Notebook cell outputs can be mirrored into their own tab, side by side with the notebook, enabling simple dashboards with interactive controls backed by a kernel.
4. Multiple views of documents with different editors or viewers enable live editing of documents reflected in other viewers. For example, it is easy to have a live preview of Markdown, Delimiter-separated Values, or Vega/Vega-Lite documents.

To navigate the user interface, JupyterLab offers customizable keyboard shortcuts and the ability to use keymaps from vim, emacs, and Sublime Text in the text editor. JupyterLab is served from the same server and uses the same notebook document format as the classic Jupyter Notebook.

The screenshot displays the JupyterLab interface. On the left, there is a sidebar with sections for Files, Running, Commands, Cell Tools, and Tabs. The main area is divided into several panes:

- Files:** A list of notebooks including Data.ipynb, Fasta.ipynb, Julia.ipynb, Lorenz.ipynb (selected), R.ipynb, iris.csv, lightning.json, and lorenz.py.
- Code Editor:** Shows the Lorenz.ipynb notebook with text: "In this Notebook we explore the Lorenz system of differential equations:" followed by the equations:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{x} &= \sigma(y - x) \\ \dot{y} &= \rho x - y - xz \\ \dot{z} &= -\beta z + xy\end{aligned}$$
 Below the equations, it says: "Let's call the function once to view the solutions. For this set of parameters, we see the trajectories swirling around two points, called attractors." A code cell contains:


```
In [4]: from lorenz import solve_lorenz
t, x_t = solve_lorenz(N=10)
```
- Output View:** Shows a 3D plot of the Lorenz attractor. Above the plot are sliders for parameters: sigma (10.00), beta (2.67), and rho (28.00).
- Code Console:** Shows the Python code for solving the Lorenz system:


```
9 def solve_lorenz(N=10, max_time=4.0, sigma=10.0, beta=8./3, rho=28.0):
10     """Plot a solution to the Lorenz differential equations."""
11     fig = plt.figure()
12     ax = fig.add_axes([0, 0, 1, 1], projection='3d')
13     ax.axis('off')
14
15     # prepare the axes limits
16     ax.set_xlim((-25, 25))
17     ax.set_ylim((-35, 35))
18     ax.set_zlim((5, 55))
19
20     def lorenz_deriv(x_y_z, t0, sigma=sigma, beta=beta, rho=rho):
21         """Compute the time-derivative of a Lorenz system."""
22         x, y, z = x_y_z
23         return [sigma * (y - x), x * (rho - z) - y, x * y - beta * z]
24
25     # Choose random starting points, uniformly distributed from -15 to 15
26     np.random.seed(1)
27     x0 = -15 + 30 * np.random.random((N, 3))
28
```

Figure 3. Example of a JupyterLab Dashboard (<https://jupyterlab.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>)

3.a.3 ROOT Framework

ROOT is a software framework for data analysis and I/O: a powerful tool to cope with the demanding tasks typical of state-of-the-art scientific data analysis. Among its prominent features are an advanced graphical user interface, ideal for interactive analysis, an interpreter for the C++ programming language, for rapid and efficient prototyping, and a persistence mechanism for C++ objects used also to write every year petabytes of data recorded by the Large Hadron Collider experiments. The ROOT Data Analysis Framework itself is written in and heavily relies on the C++ programming language: some knowledge about C++ is required. It is available for many operating systems such as Linux, Mac OS X, Windows... Obtaining the latest ROOT version is straightforward. Just choose your preferred installation method from the install page (ROOT, n.d).

Figure 4. Example of a visualization made with ROOT framework (<https://root.cern.ch/root/html/doc/guides/primer/ROOTPrimer.html>)

3.a.4 GatsbyJS

Gatsby is a framework for creating blazing fast websites and web applications. It connects the best parts of React, webpack, react-router, GraphQL, and other front-end tools into one very enjoyable developer experience. Also, it is far more like a modern front-end framework than a static site generator of old.

It uses powerful preconfiguration to build a website that uses only static files for incredibly fast page loads, service workers, code splitting, server-side rendering, intelligent image loading, asset optimization, and data prefetching. Gatsby transforms a developed website into a directory with a single HTML file and the static assets. This folder can be uploaded to any hosting provider, and that's it. Gatsby is made to collect the data from wherever it may be: Markdown, JSON, your favorite CMS, third party APIs, anywhere! And at build time, it creates an internal GraphQL server of all of this data. So, in react components, all of the data is queried at build time from that same place, in the same way through GraphQL. Gatsby has not been around for too long, but already has great documentation, and several starters to help you get a site up quickly.

3.a.5 Binder

Binder is a tool that can turn Jupyter notebooks from GitHub repositories into interactive notebooks and

that simplifies the process of making those notebooks available to anyone without dealing with it locally on the machine. The key is to just make a right setup so that it can create our custom docker image (docker image will be explained in the subheading 4.4) and what's great about it is that besides the right setup and to give a link of the repository and its certain branch if we want to. The problem is that the process of building the Docker image can get too slow sometimes especially in our bio Dynamo environment. That's why we've decided to make our own custom Docker image so that we speed up that process and make the user experience much better than it would be with just using Binder on its own.

3.a.6 Docker

Docker is a tool that enables the delivery of software in a form of packages called containers. As written in an article from opensource.com (OpenSource, n.d), *containers allow a developer to package up an application with all of the parts it needs, such as libraries and other dependencies, and deploy it as one package. By doing so, thanks to the container, the developer can rest assured that the application will run on any other Linux machine regardless of any customized settings that machine might have that could differ from the machine used for writing and testing the code.* In a way, Docker is a bit like a virtual machine. But unlike a virtual machine, rather than creating a whole virtual operating system, Docker allows applications to use the same Linux kernel as the system that they're running on and only requires applications to be shipped with things not already running on the host computer. This gives a significant performance boost and reduces the size of the application. And importantly, Docker is open-source. This means that anyone can contribute to Docker and extend it to meet their own needs if they need additional features that aren't available out of the box.

Docker uses a client-server architecture. The Docker client talks to the Docker daemon, which does the heavy lifting of building, running, and distributing your Docker containers. The Docker client and daemon can run on the same system, or you can connect a Docker client to a remote Docker daemon. The Docker client and daemon communicate using a REST API, over UNIX sockets or a network interface

Figure 5. Docker architecture shown graphically (<https://docs.docker.com/get-started/overview/>)

An image is a read-only template with instructions for creating a Docker container. Often, an image is based on another image, with some additional customization. A container is a runnable instance of an

image. You can create, start, stop, move, or delete a container using the Docker API or CLI. You can connect a container to one or more networks, attach storage to it, or even create a new image based on its current state.

b. BioDynaMo Notebook Service Updates

The idea of interactive notebooks available online for BioDynaMo was there before. Binder was used for them but it was only available to the people who've had the GitHub repository for that Binder setup (because the link of the repository is required), but thanks to the website frontend updates, it is reachable to everyone easily, and users don't have to set up anything, just click on the button Run now and voila: the chosen notebook is opened in a new tab and can be used right away. Adding the buttons was an easy part, but making sure that all of the notebooks were displayed on the tutorials properly, and making the interactive notebooks build-time short as possible was a more challenging part.

3.b.1 Frontend Updates

The official BioDynaMo website was built with GatsbyJS and some modifications were added to it to make these Notebooks available to everyone who visits this website. It's on the Tutorials dashboard page and we can see there are multiple cards for different kinds of simulations (see Figure 6).

Figure 6. Tutorials page on biodynamo.org

The cards shown on the figure above are there to represent different Notebooks for different visualizations which are the same as the one taken from the 'notebooks' directory placed in the BioDynaMo installation folder (if we choose to install it, but the installation is not required if someone just wants to use it). For every tutorial Notebook which is offered by the BioDynaMo, there is a separate card with its thumbnail and the two buttons below. The button 'View now' is used for opening that certain Notebook generated into HTML format so that it's not editable, just for viewing.


```

Diffusion

This model creates 8 cells at each corner of a cube, and one in the middle. The cell in the middle secretes a substance. The cells are modeled to move
according to the extracellular gradient, in this case to the middle.

In [1]: %load_ext autoreload; %autoreload 2; %load_notebook "1 (BONUS) <math>R_{\text{secretion}}</math>.C";

In [2]: #include <vector>
#include "bodydmo.h"
#include "diffusion_biology_modules.h"

Initialize bodydmo

In [3]: Simulation simulation("diffusion");

auto construct = [](reset Double3 position) {
  Cell* cell = new Cell(position);
  cell->GetDiameter(10);
  cell->GetMass(1.0);
  cell->AddBiologicalModule(new Chemotaxis());
  Double3 secretion_position = {10, 10, 10};
  if (position == secretion_position) {
    cell->AddBiologicalModule(new KalliumSecretion());
  }
  return cell;
};

std::vector<Double3> positions;
positions.push_back({0, 0, 0});
positions.push_back({100, 0, 0});
positions.push_back({0, 100, 0});
positions.push_back({0, 0, 100});
positions.push_back({100, 100, 0});
positions.push_back({100, 0, 100});
positions.push_back({0, 100, 100});

The cell responsible for secretion

In [4]: positions.push_back({10, 10, 10});
ModelInitializer::CreateCells(positions, construct);

Define the substances that cells may secrete

In [5]: ModelInitializer::DefineSubstance(Kallium, "Kallium", 0.4, 0, 25);

Run simulation for n timesteps

In [6]: simulation.GetScheduler()->Simulate(100);
std::cout << "Simulation completed successfully!";
Simulation completed successfully!

Let's visualize the output

In [7]: VisualizeInNotebook();

```


Figure 7. Example of an HTML Notebook

The button 'Run now' is used for opening the interactive notebook in a new tab. We see the same code as in HTML Notebooks, but this time it can be modified and compiled, just like in regular Jupyter Notebooks. What makes it so simple is that I took the advantage of Binder having a specific way of creating links from the GitHub repositories and implemented it into React components required for the Tutorials page, so that we are taken to the right place immediately, with no additional setup from the user side.

3.b.2 Querying with GraphQL

As mentioned before, GraphQL working with GatsbyJS doesn't require a regular backend, which means we don't necessarily need to have a 'usual database', because all of the data from the website can be used for querying and getting certain parameters and it doesn't refer just to one specific dataset. Thanks to Gatsby Source Plugin which sources data into the Gatsby application from the local filesystem, we've simplified the process of fetching the HTML notebooks from the directory path 'static/notebooks' (figure below).

```

},
},
{
  resolve: `gatsby-source-filesystem`,
  options: {
    path: path.join(__dirname, `static`, `notebooks`),
    name: `notebooks`,
  },
},
},
`gatsby-plugin-sharp`

```

Figure 8. Usage of gatsby-source-filesystem in the gatsby-config.js file

When we want to query data inside of this directory, we only need to add "sourceInstanceName: {eq='notebooks'}" in the query. Now we want to search for the files with .html extension, and that query can easily be written, as seen in the figure below.

Figure 9. By visiting the route '/__graphql' we can write queries to test out which data will we get

The next step was to implement this query for our tutorials page so that we fetch these HTML files' URLs together with their names. Since the thumbnails for these notebooks with a path 'static/images/notebooks' and the Binder interactive notebooks are named in the same manner as these HTML notebooks, we didn't need any other query to get the right data displayed. All that was left was to play around with the ReactJS components, to send the right props, and to properly get the values from this query and that's it, we've got everything right!

3.b.3 Docker Setup

Docker played a crucial part in this service and has helped out in a lot of ways. Firstly, we've used it for hosting the website and it also manages to deal with fetching the HTML Notebooks and thumbnails from BioDynaMo's main repository to show them on the Tutorials dashboard, as well as with the testing on how will the website look like when deployed.

Firstly, I've created BioDynaMo's Dockerfile, which is available on the DockerHub (in the 'biodynamo/notebooks' repository) which used Ubuntu system as the base image with BioDynaMo installed on it, together with some other things required for Notebooks to run (Python, Jupyter, JupyterLab, etc). The next step was to create another Docker image inside of a GitHub repository (made for our Binder setup) which will use this previously mentioned Dockerfile from DockerHub as a base image, and the commands that had to be executed inside of it were:

- Creating a default user for the system & give it some permissions,

- Copying the existing notebooks with some required C++ libraries that come with some of these notebooks,
- Running some additional scripts which enable to run Jupyter Notebook using ROOT kernel together with the BioDynaMo framework.

After the Dockerfiles were written, and our GitHub repository was prepared, it was easy to go to mybinder.org and just type in the required parameters to check whether the Docker setup was done properly.

3.b.4 JupyterLab Environment

If some user wants to use the JupyterLab environment instead of the classic Jupyter Notebook environment, all it has to do is to change /tree in the URL to /lab and that's it – JupyterLab environment is enabled!

3.b.5 Adding New BioDynaMo 'Tutorial Notebooks'

When BioDynaMo's development team decides to make a new "tutorial notebook" and someone wants to deploy it to the website, these are the requirements:

- BioDynaMo has to be installed on developer's machine, so that these notebooks from the path `biodynamo_root_directory/build/notebooks/` can be copied to the Docker container for the website afterwards (for using command `make website-live`)
- In each folder for every type of simulation (e.g Diffusion), there has to be:
 - an image which is a screenshot of that simulation added by the development team, which should be in ratio 4:3 (not strictly, but at least close to that), because these thumbnails are displayed on the Tutorials cards on www.biodynamo.org/tutorials
 - other libraries required for running this simulation properly
 - that thumbnail should be named "thumbnail.png" and the image format must be ".png"
 - HTML version of the simulation because it will be copied to the Docker container for the website, so that it can be opened online by clicking on 'View now' button
- Names of '.ipynb' notebook and the HTML notebook should be the same as the name of the folder that they're in – on the Tutorials dashboard this name of the tutorial will be automatically modified so that every first letter in a word is uppercase, and underscore (`_`) sign is replaced with blank space
- It's important to note that master branch is the only branch that gets deployed to biodynamo.org, but if we are working in some other branch and want to see how that branch would look deployed, we need to change the line `COMMAND git checkout master` inside of file named 'Website.cmake' which has a path `'BDM_ROOT_DIRECTORY/cmake'` and write the name of our development branch instead of 'master' to see how with it will look like when deployed.
- Steps from <https://biodynamo.org/docs/devguide/build/#website-related-build-targets> should be done afterwards
- Website code first goes through some tests and if everything's okay it will be deployed at 3 am (thanks to GitHub Actions Workflow YAML file)
- Every new notebook added will have its card on the Tutorials Dashboard with a thumbnail and 'View now' and 'Run now' buttons

4. CONCLUSION

BioDynaMo Notebooks service has an educational, demonstrative, and creational purpose which makes it more than just valuable for the BioDynaMo framework – it is its main advantage & makes it stand out from many biomedical simulation software.

The improvement of using this system is more than just noticeable after the integration with the website & developing the cloud service: these notebooks fetched from BioDynaMo software are now easily accessible from the biodynamo.org website. Also, having to have installed BioDynaMo with all of its requirements (such as Python with additional modules, etc..) could take up over half an hour. Getting these notebooks generated as a cloud service just from using Binder's environment would take up over 10 minutes, and using Docker's environment reduced that time to less than 2 minutes.

This was a very challenging experience for me since I didn't know that much about any of these technologies which were used for the development. It took me some time to learn how it all works and to figure out how to integrate it, but I feel very satisfied that I've learned a lot and improved my skills in the IT field. Also, I feel very honored that I was able to work with CERN and to get a project which dealt with various aspects of software development.

The next plan is to have the Notebooks' UI improved so that the simulations can be created with even less programming knowledge (which is convenient for the people from any medical field who don't want to deal with code at all).

BioDynaMo framework with its Notebooks service has a great potential to be very successful, especially in the fields of neuroscience and immunology – and now it's also expanding its focus and will deal more with epidemiology which has critical value in these times.

5. REFERENCES

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